

Data-Driven Color Classification Using the Spectrometer Module of the SENSIPATCH Wearable System

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Abstract. Accurate and portable color detection technologies are increasingly relevant in smart city contexts, where infrastructure maintenance, asset monitoring, and compliance assessment require reliable, in-situ data collection. This paper presents a wearable system for color classification based on the SENSIPATCH platform, which integrates a multi-wavelength spectrometer and machine learning-based processing. To simulate a diffusive and homogeneous optical background that mimics real-world conditions, such as urban materials placed on reflective or scattering surfaces, we placed multiple sheets of white paper behind the PANTONE samples during acquisition. This setup does not interfere directly with the light path between the sensor and the sample, but it affects the overall backscattering environment. The spectral responses obtained from six discrete LEDs were used as input features for four supervised machine learning models. Among them, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) achieved the highest classification accuracy of 93.13%. The results demonstrate the system’s feasibility as a low-cost, portable solution for automated visual inspection tasks within smart city applications.

Keywords: Color classification · Spectrometer · Wearable sensing · Machine learning · SENSIPATCH.

1 Introduction

The monitoring of color changes in urban assets such as road signs, street furniture, public installations, and painted surfaces plays a vital role in maintaining aesthetic standards, safety, and regulatory compliance in smart cities. Conventional visual inspection methods are often subjective and inefficient, while high-precision spectrometers, though accurate, are typically costly and unsuitable for widespread or wearable use.

Recent advancements in low-cost optical sensors and machine learning techniques have opened new perspectives for portable color classification systems

tailored to urban environments. These systems can enable city operators, infrastructure services, or automated agents to perform rapid, on-site inspections, contributing to real-time urban data collection and maintenance workflows.

Conventional techniques such as visual inspection and basic colorimeters often fall short in precision and consistency, especially under variable lighting or when distinguishing subtle color differences. While benchtop spectrometers offer greater accuracy, they are typically expensive, bulky, and unsuitable for portable or in-field deployment.

Advances in low-cost sensors and machine learning have opened new avenues for developing compact, data-driven color classification systems. In agricultural applications, supervised learning has been applied to calibrate color-sensitive optical sensors for fruit ripeness estimation [1]. In the biomedical space, compact spectrum measurement systems leveraging deep neural networks and specialized LED configurations have been proposed for skin-type analysis [2]. The fashion industry has seen color classification models trained on perceptually annotated datasets to categorize garment colors in online retail environments [3], while forensic applications have benefited from low-cost RGB sensors integrated into embedded systems for graffiti color signature analysis [4]. More advanced optical methods have also emerged. Hyperspectral imaging systems, such as those used for capturing facial skin tones across a wide spectral range, offer fine-grained data but come with increased cost and complexity [5]. Other efforts have explored miniaturized multispectral sensors embedded in wearable devices, achieving moderate accuracy using analog and digital neural networks [6]. IoT-based diagnostic tools such as Skinly [7] leverage different lighting modalities for detailed skin imaging, while active hyperspectral platforms have demonstrated spectral data collection in low-light conditions using broadband LED arrays [8]. Despite these contributions, many systems still struggle with either cost, portability, or adaptability for wearable use.

Among the technologies developed for compact and versatile spectral analysis, we utilize the SENSIPATCH [9] platform a compact, wearable spectroscopic sensing system developed by Sensichips [10]. The SENSIPATCH is equipped with a multi-channel scattering spectrometer, incorporating the SENSIPLUS [11] microsensor and a central photodiode surrounded by discrete-wavelength LEDs: Blue (468 nm), Green (523 nm), Yellow (593 nm), Red (645 nm), along with two near-infrared sources (850 nm and 950 nm). A lock-in amplifier is used to extract in-phase current responses from reflected light, enhancing signal fidelity under noisy or low-intensity conditions. With a small form factor (18 cm \times 18 cm), the device supports wearable deployment, enabling in-situ data collection and machine-learning-based classification. In this study, we evaluate the performance of the SENSIPATCH’s spectrometer module in classifying color shades based on the PANTONE [12] color standard, using official Pantone color cards as reference samples under scattering conditions. To simulate realistic conditions such as those encountered when sensing color through materials like skin, fabric, or coatings, we place fifteen layers of white A4 paper over the color samples.

This introduces light diffusion that degrades signal quality, offering a robust test for the sensor’s accuracy and generalizability.

The main objectives of this work are to:

- Assess the effectiveness of the SENSIPATCH system in classifying PANTONE colors under light-scattering interference.
- Develop and evaluate machine learning models that interpret spectral signals collected under challenging optical conditions.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the experimental setup, data acquisition process, and machine learning methods used for color classification. Section 3 presents the results and performance evaluation of the proposed system. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the key findings and outlines potential directions for future work.

2 Methodology

The methodology employed in this study involves three main phases. First, the experimental setup was established to control lighting and simulate scattering environments using stacked white paper layers. Second, data acquisition was performed by collecting spectral measurements using the spectrometer module of the SENSIPATCH under these controlled conditions. Finally, machine learning techniques were applied to classify the color samples based on the recorded spectral data. The goal is to evaluate the SENSIPATCH system’s ability to classify PANTONE colors when the color sample is covered by a material that both scatters light and blocks external interference. This setup helps simulate real-world conditions, such as skin or fabric, and improves signal quality, which is essential for accurate machine learning-based classification.

2.1 Experimental Setup

In contrast to the direct-contact approach used in our previous study [13], the current setup introduces an intermediate diffusive layer to simulate more realistic scenarios. Specifically, fifteen standard white A4 paper sheets were stacked and placed on top of the PANTONE color cards, which were then positioned directly above the SENSIPATCH sensor surface. Each measurement was taken with the SENSIPATCH placed beneath the PANTONE card and paper stack, ensuring stable and repeatable contact. Figure 1 illustrates the schematic representation of the experimental arrangement.

2.2 Data Acquisition

The SENSIPATCH device features a multi-channel configuration with six distinct LED channels: Blue (468 nm), Green (523 nm), Yellow (593 nm), Red (645 nm), and two Infrared LEDs at 850 nm and 950 nm. A central photodiode collects the reflected light intensity corresponding to each LED wavelength.

Fig. 1. Schematic Representation of the Experimental Setup

These signals are processed through a lock-in amplifier to extract the in-phase component of the photodiode current, which reflects the material's optical response to each wavelength.

For each color sample:

- Data was collected sequentially across all six channels.
- A sampling rate of approximately 0.62 readings per second was used.
- Each color was measured in five independent repetitions, with each repetition consisting of 1,151 continuous samples. During the first 150 samples, the spectrometer sensors were exposed to ambient conditions with no sample present. Starting from sample 151 and continuing through sample 1,151, a Pantone color card was placed on the spectrometer, with 15 white paper sheets placed on top of it for the remainder of the measurement.
- Nine PANTONE colors and plain white paper samples were tested along with a baseline (no card (AIR)), yielding a diverse dataset. Table 1 presents the PANTONE Color Codes (PCC) corresponding to each color included in the data acquisition.

To reduce ambient signal interference, a baseline correction was applied. The mean signal from the first 150 samples captured without any paper or color card was used to compute a baseline reference. This was subtracted from each subsequent measurement according to Equation 1:

$$X_{\text{unbiased}} = X - \text{mean}(X_{\text{baseline}}) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2 illustrates a representative example of the sensor response before and after baseline normalization. The top plot displays the raw in-phase signals, while the bottom plot demonstrates the improved alignment and clarity following baseline correction. As previously mentioned, the first 150 samples were recorded

with no object on the sensors. At sample 151, the color card was placed on the spectrometer, resulting in a sudden change in the signal, as shown in the raw signal graph. After applying baseline correction, the signal was trimmed to a consistent length of 1,000 samples.

Fig. 2. Top: Raw in-phase current response for Black (PCC: 19-4305) PANTONE sample across all LED channels. Bottom: Signal after baseline normalization using Equation 1.

2.3 Feature Description

The SENSIPATCH system directly provides six spectral sensor readings per sample, corresponding to different LED stimulus configurations as shown in Table

Table 1. PANTONE Color Codes (PCC)

Color	PCC
Lightest Sky	11-4804
Blue (Caribbean Sea)	18-4525
Black (Pirate Black)	19-4305
Caramel	16-1439
Green	7726
Yellow	7548
Purple	5125
Brown	476
Red	1797

2. These values were used as-is for classification, without any additional feature extraction or transformation. Each feature represents the current response of the photodiode under a specific LED illumination and bias setting, measured as the in-phase component.

Table 2. LED Features and Measurement Configurations. The columns represent Feature Name, LED Color (LC), and Wavelength (WL) in nanometers

Feature Name	LC	WL (nm)
OUTPORT PORT SDO DCBIASP 80 IN-PHASE	Yellow	593
OUTPORT PORT INT DCBIASP 25 IN-PHASE	Red	645
OUTPORT AUX DCBIASP 6 IN-PHASE	Infrared	950
OUTPORT SHA DCBIASP 10 IN-PHASE	Infrared	850
OUTPORT PORT RDY DCBIASP 6 IN-PHASE	Green	523
OUTPORT PORT CS DCBIASP 6 IN-PHASE	Blue	468

These raw sensor values, captured at a constant rate, were used directly as input to machine learning models without further pre-processing beyond baseline correction. Each row in the dataset represents a single timestamped reading with all six features.

2.4 Machine Learning-Based Classification

To classify the color samples under diffusive conditions, four supervised machine learning algorithms were employed:

- Support Vector Machine (SVM)
- Random Forest (RF)
- K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN)
- Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP)

Each model was trained using a 5-fold cross-validation strategy to ensure generalizability and to reduce the risk of overfitting. The input to the classifiers

consisted of six baseline-corrected spectral features per sample, corresponding to the in-phase photodiode current under six distinct LED wavelengths.

The models were configured using the following hyperparameters:

- **SVM:** Linear kernel, with probability estimates enabled and a fixed random seed (`random_state=42`).
- **RF:** 200 estimators (`n_estimators=200`) with a fixed random seed for reproducibility.
- **KNN:** Number of neighbors set to 150 (`n_neighbors=150`).
- **MLP:** Two hidden layers with 100 and 50 neurons respectively, L2 regularization coefficient $\alpha = 0.001$, and maximum iterations set to 500.

No additional feature engineering or dimensionality reduction was applied; the raw sensor values served directly as the input features. Cross-validation folds were stratified to maintain class distribution, and model training was repeated independently for each fold to assess consistency.

3 Results

The performance of four supervised machine learning algorithms, SVM, MLP, RF, and KNN, was evaluated using five-fold cross-validation. All models were trained and tested on the same dataset, collected using the diffusive paper-based setup with the SENSIPATCH spectrometer. Among these models, the SVM achieved the highest overall performance, with a mean classification accuracy of 93.13%. This indicates strong generalization and robustness of the SVM model, particularly in handling signal degradation introduced by the diffusive medium. Figure 3 illustrates a comparative view of the classification accuracies for all models.

To provide deeper insights into model stability across data splits, Table 3 lists the classification accuracy for each validation fold, as well as the mean accuracy. SVM and MLP demonstrated consistently high performance across most folds, with minimal degradation across partitions.

Table 3. Classification Accuracy (%) Across Five Folds for Each Model

Model	Fold 1	Fold 2	Fold 3	Fold 4	Fold 5	Mean
SVM	90.83	93.40	99.90	90.64	90.76	93.13
MLP	73.38	96.69	99.23	99.99	90.76	92.01
KNN	81.80	93.20	99.90	90.42	79.62	88.99
RF	72.74	81.80	81.81	86.15	73.30	79.16

To further evaluate classifier performance beyond accuracy, additional metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score were computed and are summarized in Table 4. Consistent with the accuracy results, SVM outperformed other models across all three metrics.

Fig. 3. Mean accuracy of machine learning models under 5-fold cross-validation. SVM achieved the highest mean accuracy of 93.13%.

Table 4. Performance Metrics of Machine Learning Models (Mean of 5 Folds)

Model	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-Score (%)
SVM	92.79	93.13	91.13
MLP	91.19	92.01	90.32
KNN	85.21	89.01	85.83
RF	73.16	73.00	72.87

Table 5 presents the mean and standard deviation (STD) of classification accuracy across folds for each model, highlighting stability. SVM exhibited the lowest STD (3.97), followed by RF (5.88), while MLP showed higher variance (11.03), suggesting sensitivity to specific data partitions.

Table 5. Mean and Standard Deviation (STD) of Classification Accuracies

Model	Mean (%)	STD (%)
SVM	93.13	3.97
MLP	92.01	11.03
KNN	88.99	8.34
RF	79.16	5.88

To further assess model behavior at the class level, the mean confusion matrix for the SVM model is presented in Figure 4. The matrix highlights that several classes, such as PURPLE_5125, RED_1797, and YELLOW_7548, were classified with 100% accuracy. Minor misclassifications were observed primar-

ily among spectrally similar classes, for example, BLACK_19-4305 was confused with Blue_18_4525 and GREEN_7726, and LIGHTESTSKY_4804 was misclassified as BROWN_16-1439.

	AIR	1000	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	BLACK_19-4305	0	805	0	0	0	195	0	0	0	0	
	BROWN_16-1439	0	0	889	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
	BROWN_476	0	0	0	998	0	2	0	0	0	0	
	Blue_18_4525	0	200	0	0	800	0	0	0	0	0	
	GREEN_7726	0	145	0	2	0	853	0	0	0	0	
	LIGHTESTSKY_4804	0	0	200	0	0	0	800	0	0	0	
	PURPLE_5125	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1000	0	0	
	RED_1797	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1000	0	
	WHITE_PAPER	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	999	
	YELLOW_7548	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1000
True Color		AIR	BLACK_19-4305	BROWN_16-1439	BROWN_476	Blue_18_4525	GREEN_7726	LIGHTESTSKY_4804	PURPLE_5125	RED_1797	WHITE_PAPER	YELLOW_7548
		Predicted Color										

Fig. 4. Mean Confusion Matrix for SVM

4 Conclusion

This study demonstrated the feasibility of using the spectrometer module of the SENSIPATCH wearable platform for color classification through a diffusive medium. By covering PANTONE color samples with fifteen layers of white paper, the experimental setup effectively simulated real-world scenarios such as skin or fabric interference. The classification models operated directly on the in-phase current responses from six LED wavelengths, without additional feature engineering. While the approach showed promising results, it may be limited by sensitivity to environmental noise and more complex scattering layers. Future work will focus on expanding the dataset to include a broader range of colors,

improving model generalizability, and refining the experimental setup to reduce measurement noise and enhance signal consistency.

Acknowledgment

This work was co-funded by the European Union Horizon Europe program with the project TARA (GA 101057524). Project ECS 0000024 Rome Technopole, CUP B83C22002820006. Project partially funded under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, Mission 4 Component 2 Investment 1.5 - Call for tender No. 3277 of 30 December 2021 of the Italian Ministry of University and Research, funded by the European Union - NextGenerationEU.

References

1. Shinya Ueno and Osamu Sakai. Data driven calibration of color-sensitive optical sensor by supervised learning for botanical application. *IEEE Sensors Journal*, 22(12):11915–11927, 2022.
2. Ling-Cheng Hsu, Shiang Hsu, Tan-Hsu Tan, Chia-Hsing Cheng, and Cheng-Chun Chang. Developing low-cost mobile device and apps for accurate skin spectrum measurement via low-cost spectrum sensors and deep neural network technology. *Sensors*, 22(22):8844, 2022.
3. Zhi Li, Gautam Golwala, Sathya Sundaram, and Jan Allebach. A data-driven approach for garment color classification in on-line fashion images. *Electronic Imaging*, 31:1–5, 2019.
4. Miguel García García, María Angélica González Arrieta, Sara Rodríguez González, Sergio Márquez-Sánchez, and Carlos Fernando Da Silva Ramos. Graffiti identification system using low-cost sensors. 2024.
5. Wanshan Zhu, Peng Sang, and Yifan He. Facial skin colour classification using machine learning and hyperspectral imaging data. *IET Image Processing*, 16(2):509–520, 2022.
6. Daniele M Crafa, Susanna Di Giacomo, Carlo Fiorini, and Marco Carminati. Neural networks embedded in wearable devices: a preliminary digital vs. analog comparison. In *2023 IEEE International Conference on Metrology for eXtended Reality, Artificial Intelligence and Neural Engineering (MetroXRINE)*, pages 587–592. IEEE, 2023.
7. Maria del Pilar Bonilla Tobar, Sven Clemann, Ralf Hagens, Sonja Pagel-Wolff, Stefan Hoppe, Peter Behm, Felicia Engelhard, Maria Langhals, Stefan Gallinat, Alex Zhavoronkov, et al. Skinly: A novel handheld iot device for validating biophysical skin characteristics. *Skin Research and Technology*, 30(3):e13613, 2024.
8. Yang Tang, Shuang Song, Shengxi Gui, Weilun Chao, Chinmin Cheng, and Rongjun Qin. Active and low-cost hyperspectral imaging for the spectral analysis of a low-light environment. *Sensors*, 23(3):1437, 2023.
9. SENSIPATCH. <https://sensichips.com/design-kit/wearables-kit/>, 2025. Accessed: 2025-05-31.
10. Sensichips. <https://sensichips.com/>, 2025. Accessed: 2025-05-31.
11. Hamza Mustafa, Mario Molinara, Luigi Ferrigno, and Michele Vitelli. A deep learning system for water pollutant detection based on the sensiplus microsensor. In *International Conference on Pattern Recognition*, pages 192–203. Springer, 2024.

12. Pantone. <https://www.pantone.com/>, 2025. Accessed: 2025-05-31.
13. Hamza Mustafa, Michele Vitelli, Filippo Milano, Mario Molinara, Luigi Ferrigno, Andrea Ria, Federico Fina, and Fabio Leccese. Preliminary evaluation of machine learning approaches for pantone color classification with the sensipatch wearable system. In *2025 IEEE International Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference (I2MTC)*, pages 1–6, 2025.